

**PLANCK - EINSTEIN - HAWKING
THEORY
OF
QUANTUM GRAVITY**

INTRODUCTION

"The supreme goal of every theory is to make the irreducible basic elements as simple and as few as possible without having surrender the adequate representation of simple datum of experience"
-Albert Einstein

The Einstein field equations (EFE) describe how matter and energy in the Universe influence the curvature of spacetime, which we perceive as gravity.

The mathematical form:

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \kappa T_{\mu\nu}$$

$G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor that represent the curvature of spacetime.

Λ is the cosmological constant associated with vacuum energy

$g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor describing the geometry of spacetime.

κ is the Einstein gravitational constant

$$\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = 2,077 \times 10^{-43} \frac{1}{N}$$

G is the Newtonian gravitational constant, which qualifies the strength of gravity in Newton's law of gravity.

c is the speed of light in vacuum.

$T_{\mu\nu}$ is stress-energy tensor or energy-momentum tensor that encapsulates the density and flux of energy and momentum in spacetime. It is bridge between matter-energy content and the curvature of spacetime. Stress-energy tensor provides a comprehensive description of how energy and momentum are distributed and interact with the fabric of spacetime.

The Einstein gravitational constant κ , is fundamental in Einstein's Theory of General Relativity . It tells us the relationship between the geometry of spacetime and energy-matter content with in that spacetime. κ serves as "proportionality factor" that determines how matter and energy influence the curvature of spacetime.

κ scales the contribution of the stress -energy tensor in shaping the geometry described by Einstein tensor.

"Spacetime tells matter how to move; matter tells spacetime how to curve"
- John Archibald Wheeler

Einstein gravitational constant κ quantifies the coupling between energy matter content and the curvature of spacetime. It has a essential role in General Relativity which describes the dynamics of gravitational interaction.

METHODS

FUNDAMENTAL CONSTANTS

$$\text{Velocity of light, } c = 299792458 \frac{m}{s}$$

$$\text{Newton's universal gravitational constant, } G = 6,67430 \times 10^{-11} \frac{m^3}{kg s^2}$$

$$\text{Dirac constant, } \hbar = 1,054571800 \times 10^{-34} J s$$

$$\text{Planck constant, } h = 6,62607015 \times 10^{-34} J s$$

$$\text{Boltzmann constant, } k_B = 1,380649 \times 10^{-23} \frac{m^2 kg}{s^2 K}$$

EXPANSION, ACCELERATION, REPULSION

$$\text{Hubble constant, } H_0 (s^{-1}) = 2,18 \times 10^{-18} s^{-1} (\text{Planck, 2018})$$

$$\text{Cosmological constant, } \Lambda = \kappa \rho_{DE} = \frac{3H_0^2 \Omega \Lambda}{c^2} = 1,08 \times 10^{-52} \frac{1}{m^2}$$

$$\text{Dark energy density, } \rho_{DE} = \frac{3H_0^2 \Omega \Lambda c^2}{8\pi G} = 5,217 \times 10^{-10} \frac{J}{m^3}$$

$$\Omega \Lambda = 0,683$$

EINSTEIN'S GRAVITATIONAL CONSTANT

$$\kappa = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} = 2,077 \times 10^{-43} \frac{1}{N}$$

PLANCK UNITS

$$\text{Planck length, } l_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}} = 1,61625518 \times 10^{-35} m$$

$$\text{Planck time, } t_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}} = 5,39124760 \times 10^{-44} s$$

$$\text{Planck area, } l_p^2 = \frac{\hbar G}{c^3} = 2,6121 \times 10^{-70} m^2$$

$$\text{Planck volume, } l_p^3 = \left(\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} = 4,2217 \times 10^{-105} m^3$$

$$\text{Planck energy, } E_p = \frac{\hbar}{t_p} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G}} = 1,9561 \times 10^9 J$$

$$\text{Planck force, } F_p = \frac{E_p}{l_p} = \frac{\hbar}{l_p t_p} = \frac{c^4}{G} = 1,2103 \times 10^{44} N$$

$$\text{Planck pressure, } P_p = \frac{c^7}{\hbar G^2} = \frac{E_p}{l_p^3} = 4,633 \times 10^{113} Pa$$

CALCULATIONS

Quantum gravity law

$$F = G \frac{M_1 m_2}{r^2} = \frac{\hbar c N_1 N_2}{N_{\text{graviton}} 4 r^2} = \frac{N_{\text{graviton}} l_p^3 t_p N_1 N_2 \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 P_{\text{quantum}}\right)^2 \Lambda}{6 \hbar r^2} = \frac{N_1 N_2 \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 P_{\text{quantum}}\right)^2 l_p t_p}{\hbar r^2}$$

$$N_{\text{graviton}} = 2,126 \times 10^{122}; N_1 = \frac{M_1}{m_g}; N_2 = \frac{m_2}{m_g}; m_g = 7,46 \times 10^{-70} \text{ kg}; P_{\text{quantum}} = 3,79 \times 10^{51} \text{ Pa}$$

Gravitational quantum field equation

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{3\hbar}{\sqrt{N_{\text{graviton}}} N_{\text{graviton}} l_p^3 P_{\text{graviton}}} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{3\hbar}{P_{\text{quantum}} N_{\text{graviton}} 2 l_p^3 P_{\text{graviton}}} T_{\mu\nu}$$

(Uncertainty)

Planck energy

$$E_p = \frac{\hbar}{t_p} = 1,9561 \times 10^9 \text{ J}$$

Dark energy density

$$\rho_{DE} = \frac{\Lambda}{\text{K}} = \frac{3\hbar c}{\lambda_{\text{graviton}} \sqrt{N} l_p^3} = 5,2 \times 10^{-10} \frac{\text{J}}{\text{m}^3}$$

Number of gravitons

$$N_{\text{graviton}} = \frac{V_{\text{quantum}}}{\frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3} = \frac{6}{\Lambda l_p^2} = \frac{6\hbar c}{\rho_{DE} V_{\text{quantum}} l_p^3 \Lambda} = 2,126 \times 10^{122}$$

Graviton wavelenght

$$\lambda_{\text{graviton}} = \sqrt{\frac{12\pi\hbar\kappa}{l_p t_p \Lambda}} = V_{\text{quantum}} P_{\text{quantum}} \kappa = \frac{3\hbar c}{\rho_{DE} \sqrt{N} l_p^3} = 2,96 \times 10^{27} \text{ m}$$

Quantized volume

$$V_{\text{quantum}} = \frac{\hbar \kappa}{t_p \Lambda} = N_{\text{graviton}} \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 = \frac{2\sqrt{N}\lambda}{N\Lambda} = \frac{6\hbar c}{\rho_{DE} N l_p^3 \Lambda} = 3,76 \times 10^{18} \text{ m}^3$$

Quantum pressure

$$P_{\text{quantum}} = \frac{3\hbar c}{2 l_p^3 \lambda_{\text{graviton}}} = \frac{N_{\text{graviton}} \hbar c}{V_{\text{quantum}} \lambda_{\text{graviton}}} = \frac{3\hbar c}{V_{\text{inflation}} 2 l_p^3 \Lambda} = 3,79 \times 10^{51} \text{ Pa}$$

(uncertainty)

Cosmological constant

$$\Lambda = \frac{6}{N_{\text{graviton}} l_p^2} = \frac{6}{R_{\text{Schwarzschild}}^2} = \frac{E_p \kappa}{V_{\text{quantum}}} = \frac{3 \hbar c}{P_{\text{quantum}} V_{\text{inflation}} 2 l_p^3} = 1,08 \times 10^{-52} \frac{1}{m^2}$$

(uncertainty)

Inflation volume

$$V_{\text{inflation}} = \frac{P_{\text{quantum}} V_{\text{quantum}}}{\rho_{DE}} = \frac{\lambda}{\Lambda} = \frac{3 \hbar c}{P_{\text{quantum}} 2 l_p^3 \Lambda} = 2,74 \times 10^{79} m^3$$

(uncertainty)

Graviton energy

$$E_{\text{graviton}} = \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 P_{\text{quantum}} = \frac{h c}{\lambda_{\text{graviton}}} = 6,7 \times 10^{-53} J$$

Schwarzschild radius

$$R_{\text{Schwarzschild}} = \frac{2 G M}{c^2} = \sqrt{\frac{6}{\Lambda}} = \sqrt{N l_p^2} = \sqrt{\frac{3 \hbar c}{\rho_{DE} 4 \pi l_p^2}} = 2,35 \times 10^{26} m$$

Mass corresponding graviton

$$m_g = \frac{\frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 P_{\text{quantum}}}{c^2} = \frac{2 \pi \hbar}{\lambda_{\text{graviton}} c} = 7,46 \times 10^{-70} kg$$

Graviton momentum

$$p_{\text{graviton}} = \frac{2 \pi \hbar}{\lambda_{\text{graviton}}} = 2,24 \times 10^{-61} \frac{kg m}{s}$$

Mass

$$M = \frac{R_{\text{Schwarzschild}} c^2}{2 G} = \frac{4 \pi \sqrt{\frac{3 \hbar c}{\rho_{DE} 4 \pi l_p^2}} V_{\text{quantum}} P_{\text{quantum}}}{\lambda c^2} = \frac{V_{\text{quantum}} P_{\text{quantum}}}{c^2} = 1,58 \times 10^{53} kg$$

Mass-energy

$$E_{\text{mass}} = \frac{4 \pi \sqrt{\frac{3 \hbar c}{\rho_{DE} 4 \pi l_p^2}} V_{\text{quantum}} P_{\text{quantum}}}{\lambda} = V_{\text{quantum}} P_{\text{quantum}} = 1,425 \times 10^{70} J$$

PRESSURE AND INFLATION

$$G_{\mu\nu} + \frac{P_p 3 t_p}{\sqrt{N_{\text{graviton}} N_{\text{graviton}} P_{\text{graviton}}}} g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{P_p 3 t_p}{P_{\text{quantum}} 2 N_{\text{graviton}} P_{\text{graviton}}} T_{\mu\nu}$$

Planck volume

$$\hbar = P_p l_p^3 t_p \rightarrow V_{\text{Planck}} = 4,222 \times 10^{-105} m^3$$

Planck sphere volume

$$\hbar = F_p l_p t_p \rightarrow V_{\text{Planck sphere}} = \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 = 1,76855 \times 10^{-104} m^3$$

Quantum expansion volume

$$\hbar = 2 \sqrt{N_{\text{graviton}}} \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 P_{\text{quantum}} t_p \rightarrow V_{\text{expansion}} = 5,158 \times 10^{-43} m^3$$

Quantized volume

$$\hbar = \rho_{DE} \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 N_{\text{graviton}} t_p \rightarrow V_{\text{quantum}} = 3,761 \times 10^{18} m^3$$

Volume of graviton horizon

$$R_{\text{graviton horizon}} = \sqrt{\frac{N l_p^2}{4}} = \frac{V_{\text{quantum}} P_{\text{quantum}}}{F_{\text{planck}}} = \sqrt{\frac{3 \hbar c}{\rho_{DE} 16 \pi l_p^2}} \rightarrow V_{\text{graviton horizon}} = \frac{V_{\text{inflation}}}{4} = 6,85 \times 10^{78} m^3$$

Inflation volume

$$\hbar = \frac{P_{\text{quantum}} V_{\text{inflation}} 2 l_p^2 \Lambda t_p}{3} \rightarrow V_{\text{inflation}} = 2,74 \times 10^{79} m^3$$

Schwarzschild horizon volume

$$R_{\text{Schwarzschild}} = \sqrt{N l_p^2} = \sqrt{\frac{3 \hbar c}{\rho_{DE} 4 \pi l_p^2}} \rightarrow V_{\text{Schwarzschild}} = 2 \times V_{\text{inflation}} = 5,48 \times 10^{79} m^3$$

Volume of observable Universe

$$V_{\text{observable universe}} = 3,57 \times 10^{80} m^3$$

Graviton momentum boundry volume

$$\hbar = p_{\text{graviton}} 2 R_{\text{Schwarzschild}} \rightarrow V_{\text{momentum boundry}} = 16 \times V_{\text{inflation}} = 4,39 \times 10^{80} m^3$$

DERIVATION OF NATURAL CONSTANTS

Dirac and Planck constant

$$\hbar = P_p l_p^3 t_p = F_p l_p t_p = 2 \sqrt{N_{\text{graviton}}} \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 P_{\text{quantum}} t_p = \rho_{DE} \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 N_{\text{graviton}} t_p$$

$$\hbar = \frac{P_{\text{quantum}} V_{\text{inflation}} 2 l_p^2 \Lambda t_p}{3} = p_{\text{graviton}} 2 R_{\text{Schwarzschild}}$$

$$h = N P_{\text{quantum}} \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 p_{\text{graviton}} \kappa = p_{\text{graviton}} \lambda_{\text{graviton}}$$

Speed of light

$$c = \frac{\sqrt{N_{\text{graviton}}} 4 \pi l_p^2}{t_p \lambda_{\text{graviton}}} = \frac{\lambda_{\text{graviton}}^2}{N 4 \pi l_p 4 \pi t_p} = \frac{\Lambda N_{\text{graviton}} l_p^3}{6 t_p}$$

Newton's gravitational constant

$$G = \frac{R_{\text{graviton horizon}} c^4}{P_{\text{quantum}} V_{\text{quantum}}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{3 \hbar c}{\rho_{DE} 16 \pi l_p^2}} c^4}{P_{\text{quantum}} V_{\text{quantum}}} = \frac{\hbar c}{4 N m_g m_g} = \frac{N_{\text{graviton}} l_p^3 t_p c^4 \Lambda}{6 \hbar} = \frac{l_p t_p c^4}{\hbar}$$

THE BLACK HOLE THERMODYNAMICS

Black hole's number of gravitons

$$N_{Blackhole} = \frac{M_{Blackhole}}{m_g}$$

Black hole's Schwarzschild radius

$$R_{Schwarzschild\ blackhole} = \sqrt{N_{graviton}} l_p^2 \frac{N_{Blackhole}}{N_{graviton}} = \frac{N_{Blackhole} \lambda_{graviton}}{4\pi N_{graviton}} = \frac{\sqrt{N_{graviton}} N_{Blackhole} l_p^3 \Lambda}{6}$$

Black hole's area

$$A = \frac{4\pi l_p^2 N_{Blackhole}^2}{N_{graviton}} = \frac{4\pi l_p^4 N_{Blackhole}^2 \Lambda}{6}$$

Temperature of Hawking radiation

$$T_{Hawking} = \frac{N_{graviton} P_{quantum} \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3}{2\pi N_{Blackhole} k_B} = \frac{6\hbar}{N_{Blackhole} l_p t_p k_B \Lambda \lambda_{graviton}} = \frac{4\pi l_p^2 P_{quantum} 4\sqrt{N_{graviton}}}{N_{Blackhole} k_B \Lambda \lambda_{graviton}}$$

Bekenstein-Hawking entropy

$$S_{Bekenstein-Hawking} = \frac{\pi l_p^2 N_{Blackhole}^2 k_B \Lambda}{6}$$

Bekenstein-Hawking luminosity

$$L = \frac{\sqrt{N_{graviton}} 2\pi \hbar c^2}{80 \times \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 N_{Blackhole}^2 \Lambda \lambda_{graviton}}$$

Black holes evaporation time

$$t_{ev} = \frac{80 \times \frac{4}{3} \pi l_p^3 N_{Blackhole}^3 \Lambda}{\sqrt{N_{graviton}} c}$$